

Arachnozoogeographical analysis of the boundary between Eastern Palearctic and Indomalayan Region

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Abstract: This study aims to test how the distribution of various orders of Arachnida follows the classical subdivision of Asia and where the transitional zone between the Eastern Palearctic (Holarctic Kingdom) and the Indomalayan Region (Paleotropical) is situated. This boundary includes Thar Desert, Karakorum, Himalaya, a band in Central China, the line north of Taiwan and the Ryukyu Islands.

The conclusion is that most families of Arachnida (90), excluding most of the representatives of Acari, are common for the Palearctic and Indomalayan Regions. There are no endemic orders or suborders in any of them. Regarding Arachnida, their distribution does not justify the sharp difference between the two Kingdoms (Paleotropical and Holarctic) in Eastern Eurasia. The transitional zone (Sino-Japanese Realm) of HOLT et al. (2013) also does not satisfy the criteria for outlining an area on the same footing as the Palearctic and Indomalayan Realms.

Key words: Palearctic, Indomalayan, Arachnozoogeography, Arachnida

According to the classical subdivision the Indomalayan Region is formed from the regions in Asia that are south of the Himalaya, and a zone in China. North of this "line" is the Palearctic (consisting of different subregions). This "line" (transitional zone) is separating two kingdoms, therefore the differences between them should be substantial.

Geography

Eastern Palearctic

The Eastern Palearctic is spread (very conditionally) east of the Jenisey River (Johansen Line, JOHANSEN, 1955), Caspian Sea and Turkey, and goes as far as Japan, China and Nepal. It is characterised by boreal (taiga) regions, steppe grasslands and deserts. Then it follows the high mountains (Pamir, Tienshan, Hindukush, Karakorum, Himalaya, the mountains of the Far East). The problems of the line (transitional zone) which separates it from the Indomalayan Region (and the Paleotropical), arise in Nepal, India, China and Japan (the Ryukyus).

Central Asia and the Iranian Plateau are home to dry steppe grasslands and desert basins, with mountain forests, woodlands, and grasslands in the

region's high mountains and plateaus. In southern Asia the boundary of the Palearctic is largely altitudinal. The foothills of the Himalaya with average altitude between about 2000 – 2500 m a.s.l. form the boundary between the Palearctic and Indomalaya Ecoregions.

China, Korea and Japan have more humid and temperate climate (as compared to the adjacent Siberia and Central Asia), and are home to rich temperate coniferous, broadleaf, and mixed forests, which currently are mostly limited to mountainous areas, as the densely populated lowlands and river basins have been subjected to intensive agricultural use and urbanisation.

Indomalayan Region

The tropical part of Eurasia and the archipelagos south of it form a subkingdom of the Paleotropical Kingdom of Engler. The name used by SCLATER (1858) was Indian Region, by WALLACE (1876) – Oriental Region, other zoogeographers follow DARLINGTON (1957) and UDVARDY (1975) to call it Indomalayan Region or Realm. It consists of the southernmost territories of China, Taiwan, India, Sri Lanka, Indochina, and the islands of Indonesia

and Malaysia up to the Lydekker's Line (including Wallacea as a subregion). GEPTNER (1936) and others include Wallacea into the Australian Region (Notogea). Characteristic for these regions is the hot or warm climate, which allows the presence of orders like Amblypygi, Uropygi, Schizomida and other thermophile groups. Typical (but declining fast) are also the humid tropical forests. Arid areas (i.e. in India) are much less abundant which determines the scarcity of groups like Solifugae and Scorpiones. The delimitation of Sclater – Wallace is based entirely on land vertebrates, with the flora and invertebrates of Papuan Area being predominantly Indomalayan. DARLINGTON (1957) includes New Guinea in the Australian Region.

The western border of the Indomalayan Region runs across the Tar Desert, where the Indian fauna is mixed with the one of West Asia. In the Himalaya the northern border is very interesting, as within small distance Indomalayan elements meet with animals from another Kingdom – the Holarctic. Across China there is a large band running between the Huanhe and Yangtzekiang (Hwang Ho and Yangtze) Rivers (HOFFMANN 2001, MORRONE, 2015). The biogeographers and some zoogeographers (LOPATIN, 1989) clearly include the Papuan Area (Subregion?) in the Indomalayan Region, while according to KRIZHANOVSKIY (1976) the Papuan endemics are originating mostly from the Paleotropics. According some specialists (GEPTNER, 1936, LOPATIN, 1989) the central part of the Pacific also belongs to the Indomalayan Region, while according others (UDVARDY, 1975) Melanesia and all Pacific islands form the Oceania Biogeographical Realm. For RIBEIRO et al. (2014) the "Oriental Region" is not a separate area, but it is merged with the East Palearctic.

East Asia was not much affected by glaciations in the ice ages, and retained 96 % of Pliocene tree genera, while Europe retained only 27 %. In the subtropical region of southern China and in the southern edge of the Himalaya, the transition from the Palearctic temperate forests to the subtropical and tropical forests of Indomalaya results in a rich and diverse mix of plant and animal species. The mountains of South-West China are also designated as a biodiversity hotspot. In south-East Asia, high mountain ranges form tongues of Palearctic flora and fauna in northern Indochina and southern China (FAN, 1990). Isolated small outposts (sky islands) occur as far south as central Myanmar (on Nat Ma Taung, 3050 m), northernmost Vietnam (on Fan Si Pan, 3140 m), and the high mountains of Taiwan.

In the Indian Ocean, the Andaman Islands and the Nicobar Islands are two island groups, separated by the 10° N parallel, with the Andamans to the north, and the Nicobars to the south. The total land area of the territory is approximately 6496 km². The islands are situated in the Bay of Bengal, and geographically are part of South-East Asia, 150 km north of Aceh in Indonesia. They are separated from Thailand and Burma by the Andaman Sea.

The tropical Pacific islands are sometimes assigned the status of a subregion to the Australian Region (GEPTNER, 1936, DE LATTIN, 1967, BUCAR, 1983), or given the rank of a separate Polynesian Region (BOBRINSKIY, ZENKEVITCH & BIRSTEIN, 1945), Polynesian Region within the Kingdom Paleogea (LOPATIN, 1989), or "Oceania Realm" (UDVARDY, 1975, HOLT et al., 2013). Biogeographically these islands are closer to the "Oriental" Region (MORRONE, 2015). Moreover, the "typical" for Australia vertebrate fauna is not represented on these islands. Many arachnologists contributed to the study of the arachnids of these oceanic islands (i.e. BEIER 1940, COKENDOLPHER & TSURUSAKI 1994, BERLAND 1934, LEHTINEN 1996).

ARLDT (1908) related the distribution of some orders of Arachnida with the geological age of the continents. Among the modern ideas about the development of South-East Asia we must mention the papers of AUDLEY-CHARLES et al. (1972, 1981), AUDLEY-CHARLES (1984), HALL (1997, 1998, 2001, 2002), HALL & HOLLOWAY (Eds.) (1998), GOLONKA et al. (2006), WANG HONGZHEN (Ed.) (1985), including the classical papers of WALLACE (1869), LYDEKKER (1896), and WEBER (1899).

Many other authors (KATILI (1971, 1975, 1978, WILSON & MOSS, 1999, BRIGGS, 1995, PROCHES & RAMDHANI, 2012, METCALFE, 2002, TURNER, HOVENKAMP & WELZEN, 2001, COX, 2001, DASSMAN, 1976, GREHAN, 1988, HEWER, 1971, HORTON, 1973, KREFT & JETZ, 2010, 2013, LOHMAN ET AL., 2006, MARUYAMA, SENO & LIU, 1989, MORRONE, 2002, 2004, PATHIRANA, 1980, SCHMIDT, 1954, VORIS, 2000 and others) have discussed the very notions of natural regions, subregions and provinces. Sokolov et al. (1986) discussed the place of Mongolia in the zoogeographical subdivision of the Palearctic (again based on mammals).

The existence of Gondwana was discussed by MILLOT (1952, 1957) and LEGENDRE & CASSAGNE-MEGEAN (1968). According to McELHINNY, HAILE & CRAWFORD (1974), palaeomagnetic evidence shows that the Malay Peninsula was not a part of Gondwanaland. Other authors (STAUFFER, 1974,

STAUFFER & GOBBETS, 1972), on the contrary, speculate that South-East Asia belonged to Gondwana, with all consequences for its rich fauna.

Malay Archipelago

Geography, General Zoogeography and Paleogeography

Situated between the Indian and Pacific Oceans, the group of over 25,000 islands is the archipelago with the largest area in the world. It includes Indonesia, the Philippines, Singapore, Brunei, East Malaysia and East Timor. The islands of New Guinea are not included in the definitions of the Malay Archipelago. The recent biogeography of the "Indo-Australian Archipelago" has been outlined by LOHMAN et al. (2011).

In the present study the notion "Malay Archipelago" includes only Indonesia (without Papua), East Timor and Northern Borneo (Sarawak, Sabah and Brunei). The biggest islands are as follows:

Borneo – area 743 330 km², highest point Kinabalu (4095 m a.s.l.)

Sumatra – area 473 481 km², highest point Kerinci (3805 m a.s.l.)

Sulawesi – area 174 600 km², highest point Rantemario (3478 m a.s.l.)

Java – area 132 187 km², highest point Semeru (3676 m a.s.l.)

Bali – area 5,633 km², highest point Agung (3142 m a.s.l.)

Lombok – area 4,725 km², highest point Rinjani (3726 m a.s.l.)

Flores – area 13,540 km², highest point Poco Mandasawu (2370 m a.s.l.)

Timor – area 30,777 km², highest point Tatamailau (2963 m a.s.l.)

We have to consider the analysis of MOSS & WILSON (1998) concerning the biogeographical implications of the events on Sulawesi and Borneo during the Tertiary. According to them Wallacea is a biogeographical area with intermediate position between the Asian and Australian flora and fauna with organisms of high level of endemism. The land connection between Borneo and continental SE Asia might have existed during an important period of the Tertiary and could have allowed migrations of species. Western Sulawesi has been connected with East Borneo by Late Cretaceous and Early Eocene (more than 50 Ma) with option of dispersion of fauna. The ophiolytes of East Sulawesi have been accreted to Sulawesi in the Late Oligocene and resulted

in a more extensive land of the large (174 600 km²) island. "Microcontinental fragments accreted onto eastern Sulawesi in the Miocene to Pleistocene may have been emergent as they drifted towards Sulawesi and allowed island hopping or rafting for biota of Australian affinity. Island hopping routes for the dispersal of organisms between Borneo-Sulawesi and the Philippines may have existed along volcanic arcs, such as the long-lived North Sulawesi arc" (MOSS & WILSON, 1998).

Here is the timing of events in the distribution of the elements of land in the area (according to AUDLEY-CHARLES, 1984):

1. Australia/New Guinea splits from Antarctica (ca. 53 Ma)

2. Postulated formation of Philippines by collision of an Asian continental fragment with an island arc (Oligocene)

3. Possible land connection(s) across Makassar Strait (mid-Miocene)

4. Collision between New Guinea and a Tertiary island arc (ca. 15 Ma)

5. Submarine collision between Gondwanaland (Sula Peninsula) and Laurasia at or near East Sulawesi (ca. 15 Ma)

6. Island chain established between East Sulawesi and Australia (Late Miocene to Late Pliocene)

7. Collision between parts of Gondwanic Outer Banda Arc and Laurasian (volcanic) Inner Banda Arc (Late Miocene to Early Pliocene)

8. Gulf of Bone opens (about the same time)

9. Probable land connection(s) across South Makassar Strait (from Late Pliocene)

KEAST (1983) analysed the separation sequence of the Southern Continents. According to BIRD, TAYLOR & HUNT (2005) during the last glacial period there was a savannah corridor in Sundaland. SANMARTIN (2002) outlined the Paleogeographic History of the Southern Hemisphere.

The boundary across the mountains

MARTENS (1984) concluded from his long studies of the Himalaya, that "both climatic belts and vegetation zones are largely in accordance with the areas of origin outside the Himalayas of the various faunal elements. The Himalayan fauna is mainly an immigration fauna. We distinguish five main centres of origin and thus five categories of Himalayan fauna, three of which fall into the Palearctic (Central Asian, Himalayan West Asian, Himalayan West Chinese), and two in the Oriental realm (Himalayan Indochinese, Peninsular Indian". Actually, the Himalayas are very young mountains.

In the Pleistocene, their altitude would have been only half of the present 8848 m. There are no water divides between Tibet and the Indo-Gang Plain. Big rivers flow from the Kailas Range in South Tibet and cross epigenetically the Main Himalayan Chain.

When trekking along Kali Gandaki River one have the strange feeling to cross a boundary between two kingdoms – the Holarctic and the Paleotropic.

In his analysis of the distribution of mammals in the Himalayan ranges HOFFMANN (2001) concludes that, because of the strong altitudinal gradient, “paleo-arctic elements dominate higher, and Indomalayan elements, lower elevations” (being in the Himalaya almost equally represented). Further, HOFFMANN (2001) analyses in details the transitional zone in such a complicated area as North Burma, Sichuan and Yunnan (map 1).

The boundary across China

According to CORBET (1978), the Yangtze River was “...just beyond the southern limit of the [Palearctic] region”, and further “...in lowland China the boundary is taken very arbitrarily as latitude 35°N, corresponding in part with the Hwang Ho (the Yellow River)”. The broad area between these two rivers has warm temperate climate (FAN, 1990) and is a transitional zone between the two realms. CORBET & HILL (1992) confirm the idea that the arbitrary northern boundary between the Palearctic and the Indomalayan Region is about 35°N (the Yellow River). ZHANG & ZHAO (1978) placed the median line “a little south of Yangtze”. Again CORBET & HILL (1992) defined three divisions of the transitional zone between the Hwang Ho and the Yangtze Rivers (see HOFFMANN, 2001 for details).

All these subdivisions were based on vertebrates, a group with many anthropogenic changes during the last centuries. It would be interesting to compare this discussion with the results obtained by detailed analysis of the distribution of all orders of Arachnida (so far much less known in this area). PALESTRINI & ZUNINO (1986) and PALESTRINI, SIMONIS & ZUNINO (1986) have analysed the distribution of insects in the Chinese transitional zone.

An important delimitation of the demarcation line between the Palearctic and Oriental regions in eastern China (again based on mammals) is done by HUANG (1985).

Ryukyu Islands

Ryukyu Islands (Ryūkyū-shotō), known in Japanese as the Nansei-shotō, lit. “Southwest Islands”, and also known as the Ryukyu Arc are a chain of more than 100 volcanic Japanese islands that stretch

of 1100 km southwest from Kyushu to Taiwan: the Ōsumi, Tokara, Amami, Okinawa, and Sakishima Islands (further divided into the Miyako and Yaeyama Islands), with Yonaguni being the southernmost. The largest of the islands is Okinawa. The surface of the achipelago is 4642 km², the highest point is at 1936 m a.s.l. (Mt. Myianoura – dake). The two largest islands are Okinawa (1204 km²) and Amami Great Island (712 km²). Ryukyu Islands are defined as oceanic islands (MILLIEN-PARRA & JAEGER, 1999).

The islands have a subtropical climate with mild winters and hot summers. Precipitation is very high, and is affected by the rainy season and typhoons. Except the outlying Daitō Islands, the island chain has two major geologic boundaries: the Tokara Strait, between the Tokara and Amami Islands, and the Kerama Gap, between the Okinawa and Miyako Islands.

Watase’s Line, which crosses the Tokara Islands, marks a major biogeographic boundary. The north of the line belongs to the Palearctic Region while the southern portion is the northern limit of the Oriental Region. Yakushima in Ōsumi is the southern limit of the Palearctic Region. It is featured with millennium-old cedar trees. The island is part of Kirishima-Yaku National Park and was designated as World Heritage Site by UNESCO in 1993.

The south of Watase’s Line is recognised by ecologists as a distinct subtropical moist broadleaf forest ecoregion. The flora and fauna of the islands have much in common with Taiwan, the Philippines, and South-East Asia, and are part of the Indomalaya ecozone.

Approximately one half of the amphibian species of the islands are endemic.

The northern Ryukyu Islands are separated from Kyushu by the so-called “Myake Line”.

Taiwan and the Ryukyus is included in the Palearctic Region by BUCAR (1983). The present author includes them in the Indomalayan Region.

The Transition Zone

FERRO & MORRONE (2014) discussed the very notion of the transition zone and defined it as follows: “A biogeographical transition zone is defined as a geographical area of overlap, with a gradient of replacement and partial segregation between biotic components (sets of taxa that share a similar geographical distribution as a product of a common history). It is an area where physical features, environmental conditions and ecological factors allow the mixture and the co-occurrence of two or more biotic components, but also constrain their distribution further into one another”.

Map 1. Biogeographical subdivision of the world (according to HOLT et al. 2012)

Another definition was formulated by PALESTRINI & ZUNINO (1986): “the transition among biogeographical regions is a phenomenon that starts when a possibility of biotic exchange, among different regions (two at least), is established. It finishes when an effective barrier among the regions is re-established”.

We discussed already the map and the analysis on mammals (HOFFMANN, 2001). Recently MORRONE (2015) published a biogeographic map, showing the “Chinese Transitional Zone”. A higher category has been assigned to this (or a similar) zone in the subdivision of HOLT et al. (2012): an independent “Sino-Japanese Realm”.

WOODRUFF (2003) analysed the location of the Indochinese-Sundaic biogeographic transition in plants and birds.

General Zoogeography

While comparing the Palearctic and Indomalayan Regions, it is worth to analyse the Eastern Palearctic. In its northern part are the latitudinal zones of tundra, taiga and mixed forests, then the vast arid plains of Central Asia and Mongolia and high mountains. Parts of the Eastern Palearctic are also the chain of islands along the east coast of Asia: Sahalin, Kuril Islands and the main islands of Japan (GEPTNER, 1936, BOBRINSKIY, ZENKEVICH & BIRSTEIN, 1946, KUZNETSOV, 1950, 1957, KRIZHANOVSKIY, 1980, 2002, LOPATIN, 1989). Particular biota exists in the Russian Primorie, Manjuria and Korea (KURENTOV, 1965; KOLOSOV, 1980).

The “Oriental” (Indomalayan) Region was outlined, as many other regions, mostly following the distribution of terrestrial vertebrates (DARLINGTON, 1957, DE LATTIN, 1967, GREHAN, 1988, LOMOLINO et al., 2006). Some scientists (GRESSITT, 1961), how-

ever, insist that the insect distribution follows quite different patterns and the boundary between the Indomalayan and the Australian Regions (between Paleotropicalia and Notogea) should be moved far to the East, to include not only the whole of Micronesia and Polynesia, placed originally by Wallace in the Australian Region, but also parts or even the whole of the Papuan Subregion (New Guinea, the Bismarck and Solomon Islands and even North Queensland). Advocating this point of view was one of the foremost researchers of the insect fauna of the Pacific, Dr L. Gressitt. In many papers he emphasised that “the Oriental Region influence dominates the fauna of the mid-Pacific, as well as western Pacific islands” (GRESSITT, 1961). His monograph “Problems in the Zoogeography of Pacific and Antarctic islands” (GRESSITT, 1961) suggests to compare the patterns and the conclusions obtained by the entomologist with these obtained by the study of some other invertebrates. They share the paleogeographic development of the area, but the different groups (vertebrates, land snails, various orders of insects, land isopods, Myriapoda, Arachnida and others) certainly have followed their own ways, according to their age, spreading capacity, ability to establish themselves to new places, etc. We find particularly interesting to analyse the distribution of such wingless groups as Isopoda, Arachnida, Myriapoda and Gastropoda. Their study already proved elsewhere to be of great value (VANDEL, 1972). Actually, the “small animals” are important when studying the Gondwanan and other paleodistributions (HARVEY, 1996).

Some subdivisions of the Indomalayan Region

Geptner (1936) – Oriental (Indo-Malayan) Region, divided into Indian (India, South China,

Indochina, and Ryukyu) and Malayan (Malacca, Sunda Islands and Philippin Islands)

BOBRINSKIY, ZENKEVITCH & BIRSTEIN (1946) – Paleogea – Indomalayan Region

DARLINGTON (1957) – Megagea – Indomalayan Region

DE LATTIN (1967) – Megagea – Oriental (Indian) Region

MÜLLER (1974) – Palaeotropical Realm – Oriental Region

UDVARDY (1975) – Indomalayan Biogeographical Realm

LEHTINEN (1980) – Indo-Pacific Region with centers of speciation: South India and Ceylon, East-Himalaya – Indochina, Malayan Archipelago

KRIZHANOVSKIY (1980) – Paleotropical (Paleogean) Dominion – Indo-Malayan Region

KRIZHANOVSKIY (2002) divides the region into three subregions – Malayan, Indian and Indochinese

LOPATIN (1980) – Paleogea – Indo-Malayan Region

PROCHEŞ & Randhani (2002) – Indo-Malayan Region

HOLT et al. (2002) – Oriental and Sino-Japanese Realms

Paleogeography

Siberia is one of the most ancient continental masses (METELKIN, VERNIKOVSKY & KAZANSKY, 2012, YIN & HARRISON, Eds, 1996). The paleogeography of South China and the adjacent territories is presented in the Atlas of WANG HONGZHEN, Ed. (1985), of Japan – by MARUYAMA, ISOZAKI, KIMURA & TERABAYASHI (1997). The ecological changes in the Palaearctic Region since the Pliocene have been reviewed by MOREAU (1955). GLUSHKOVA (1992) outlined the paleogeography of the Late Pleistocene glaciation of North-East Asia. The Quaternary fauna and the climatic fluctuation in the tropical zone of China have been analysed by HUANG ZHENGUO & ZHANG WEIQIANG (2003), the zoogeographical regions of China – by ZHANG & ZHAO (1978).

The Hainan Island had been connected with the mainland until the Miocene, when faulting caused subsidence and brought about the formation of the Qiongzhou Strait (WANG HONGZHEN, Ed., 1985). The biogeographic analysis of HUA ZHU (2016) indicates the low endemism of the flora (only seven endemic genera out of 1283), and concludes that “the Hainan Island could have been adjacent to northern Vietnam and the Guangxi at least in the Eocene”.

Laurasia, the name of the northern superconti-

nent, which was detached from Pangaea by 200 Ma, came from the fusion of the names of Laurentia (the North American craton) and Eurasia. The supercontinent consisted roughly of Laurentia, Siberia, Baltica, Kazakhstania, and the cratons of North China and East China. Laurasia is considered a Mesozoic phenomenon.

Angarida is defined as a hypothetical continent, having existed about the area of today's North Asia since the Late Ordovician to the Mesozoicum (included).

The collision between the Indian subcontinent and the Eurasian continent has started in the Paleogene and continues today. The Indian plate continues to move northward relative to Asia with about 5 cm per year (SAHNI & KUMAR, 1974). The development of the Himalaya was outlined by ALLEGRE et al. (1984), YIN & HARRISON (2000), LE FORT (1996), COLCHEN (1981) and others. The biogeography of the Indian subcontinent was discussed in details by MANI (1974), BLASCO (1981) and many others.

To quote BRIGGS (1989): “If India broke its contact with the other continents sometime around 148 Ma and, if it existed as an isolated, oceanic continent until the Early Miocene, its fossil terrestrial and shallow marine biota should demonstrate the evolutionary effects of more than 100 m.y. of isolation. This means that India should have developed a peculiar biota with a high percentage of distinct genera and families. But, with the possible exceptions ...the expected preponderance of peculiar organisms has simply not been found”.

Ryukyu. Between 1.6 – 1.3 Ma, the East China Sea area, including most of the Okinawa Trough, may have been sub aerial. At that time, the Ryukyu Arc region may have been a part of the Eurasian continent. Extensive subsidence may have occurred at the second stage, about 1.3 Ma, in the Early Pleistocene. The present Ryukyu Arc (Ryukyu Ridge) has been formed after that. The Ryukyu Arc may have been nearly connected to the Chinese continent, through Taiwan as a land bridge, sometime during the two major development periods (between 1.6 – 1.0 Ma, and 0.2 – 0.025 Ma). The paleo-land may have been submerged step by step since 0.03 Ma by both crustal movement and sea-level rising after the last Ice Age. Submarine stalactite caves at 10 – 35 m deep off the Ryukyu Islands were discovered. The caves have subsided since the Würm Ice Age. Stone tools were also recovered inside one of them (KIMURA, 2000).

The Quaternary period was characterised by climatic oscillation, and due to these climatic variations and marine transgression and regression, the

Ryukyu Islands have changed greatly in terms of land configuration (KIZAKI & OSHIRO 1977, 1980; KIMURA 1996, 2000).

The Ryukyu Archipelago changed dramatically in terms of land configuration also through repeated cycles of land bridge formation and insular isolation due to the vertical and horizontal movement of the Ryukyu Cordillera and sea level changes throughout the Cenozoic era (KIZAKI & OSHIRO 1977, 1980; KIMURA 1996, 2000).

Kyushu through Taiwan and the Ryukyu Islands is known to have occurred several times, although truncation by the Tokara Gap remains controversial (KIZAKI & OSHIRO 1977, 1980; KIMURA 1996, 2000).

The period 30-0 Ma is of most interest to biogeographers since before then the separation between Asia and Australia was greater and for almost all land plants and animals it was probably not possible to cross this barrier. As a conclusion, "there were never continuous land links between Sundaland and Australia" (HALL, 2001).

The distribution of Arachnida west and east of the "lines" (of Wallace, Lydekker and Weber) has been analysed by BERON (2015), and discussed also by WHITMORE, Ed. (1981), VACHON (1982), SIMPSON (1977), MAYR (1944, 1945), CAMBRIDGE (1897).

How the known distribution of Arachnida fits into the classical scheme? Table 1).

Analysis and comments

This list contains some curious facts. If we consider all the orders of Arachnida (from the Acari are included only the Opilioacarida, the Holothyrida and the Ixodida) we can see that in both regions (Indomalayan and Palearctic) a total of 170 families live, and in both classical regions we have found records of almost equal number of families: 126 in the Indomalayan Region and 130 in the Palearctic Region. From this numbers 93 families are in common for both areas. In both areas the order Ricinulei and the suborder Paleoamblypygi are absent. In the Indomalayan Region are present all the other orders and suborders of Arachnida. In the Palearctic Region are absent also the orders Schizomida and Holothyrida. In the Palearctic are practically absent (living in very few places) also the orders Amblypygi and Uropygi.

Palpigradi

Palpigradi have not been recorded in the eastern Palearctic, they are unknown in Japan (CONDÉ, 1996).

Almost nothing is known about these tiny and rarely collected animals from the vast and mostly dry area from Turkey and Arabia to Afghanistan

(NENILIN, 1987, HARVEY, 2013e). The only exceptions are *Eukoenia juberthiei* Condé, 1974 from Lebanon and the strange *Leptokoenia gerlachi* Condé, 1965 from the Farasan Island near Saudi Arabia (type of a new genus, found the following year also in DR Congo and later in Brazilian caves). These species have been recorded from the Western Palearctic.

In the Indomalayan Region HANSEN (1901) and CONDÉ (1981, 1984, 1988, 1990, 1992a, 1992b, 1993, 1994, 1996) has recorded Palpigradi from several countries: Indonesia, Malaysia, Thailand, Hong Kong. These records include representatives of the genera *Eukoenia*, *Koeneiodes* (Eukoeniidae) and *Prokoenia* (Prokoeniidae).

Eight species have been recorded from Thailand: *Prokoenia asiatica* Condé, 1994 (Prokoeniidae), and six species of Eukoeniidae: *Eukoenia angusta* (Hansen, 1901), *E. deleta* Condé, 1992, *E. lyrifer* Condé, 1992, *E. siamensis* (Hansen, 1901), *E. thais* Condé, 1988, *Koeneiodes leclerci* Condé, 1992, and *K. spiniger* Condé, 1984. All of them are known only from this country (**endemics**). CONDÉ (1992) recorded *Koeneiodes madecassus* from Hong Kong (the first Palpigradi known from China). *Koeneiodes berndti* Condé, 1988 was described from Malaysia (Borneo). From Indonesia are known seven species: from Java, Sulawesi and Sumatra (CONDÉ, 1989, 1990, 1992, 1994). Some of them are **endemic** (*Eukoenia maros*, *E. lienhardi* – also in Brunei and Singapore, *E. paulinae*, *Prokoenia celebica*, *P. javanica*), others are known from Madagascar (*Koeneiodes madecassus*, *K. frondiger*).

Solifugae

From West to East in the Palearctic the number of Solifugae is at first increasing: 60 sp. in the tiny Israel (LEVY & SHULOV, 1964 and suppl.), many others in Middle Asia and in Pakistan (POCOCK, 1895, LAWRENCE, 1956, HARVEY, 2013b). Some species of Galeodidae and Karschiidae are still present in Mongolia (*Galeodes kozlovi* Birula, *G. mongolicus* Roewer, *Karschia mongolica* Roewer) and East China (*Galeodes caspius caspius* Birula, *G. kozlovi* Birula, *G. montivagans* Roewer, *G. przewalskii* Birula, *G. rapax* Roewer, *G. sedulous* Roewer, *G. sejugatus* Roewer, *Karschia tibetana* Hirst), none is known from Siberia (BIRULA, 1938, GROMOV, 1998, 2000, 2004, ARNOLD, , HIRST, 1907, ROEWER, 1934). The distribution and the northern limit of Solifugae in Eurasia is shown on Map 2.

In the Indian Subregion 21 species of Solifugae are known. They belong to the families Galeodidae: Daesiidae – *Gluiopsis*, Galeodidae – *Galeodes*.

Table 1. Comparison between the orders suborders and families of Arachnida in the Indomalayan and Palearctic Regions

Group	Region	
	Indomalayan	Palearctic
Order Palpigradi	Present	present
Fam. Eukoeneriidae	Present	present
Order Ricinulei	Absent	absent
Order Solifugae	present	present
Fam. Galeodidae	present	present
Fam. Karschiidae	absent	present
Fam. Daesiidae	present	present
Fam. Solpugidae	absent	present
Fam. Gylippidae	absent	present
Fam. Melanoblosiidae	present	absent
Fam. Rhagodidae	present	present
Order Scorpiones	present	present
Fam. Bothriuridae	Present (Indian Himalaya)	absent
Fam. Buthidae	present	present
Fam. Pseudochactidae	present	present
Fam. Euscorpiidae	present	present
Fam. Scorpiopidae	present	present
Fam. Chaerilidae	present	?absent
Fam. Troglotayasicidae	absent	?present
Fam. Iuridae	absent	present
Fam. Diplocentridae	absent	present
Fam. Hemiscorpiidae	absent	present
Fam. Hormuridae	present	present
Fam. Scorpionidae	present	present
Fam. Akravidae	absent	present
Order Schizomida	present	absent
Fam. Hubbardiidae	present	absent
Order Uropygi	present	present
Fam. Hypoconidae	present	present
Order Amblypygi	present	present
Suborder Neoamblypygi	present	present
Fam. Charinidae	present	present
Fam. Phrynichidae	present	absent
Fam. Phrynidae	present	absent
Suborder Paleoamblypygi	absent	absent
Order Opiliones	present	present
Suborder Cyphophthalmi	present	present
Fam. Stylocellidae	present	absent
Fam. Sironidae	absent	present
Fam. Pettalidae	present	absent
Suborder Eupnoi	present	present
Fam. Caddidae	absent	present
Fam. Phalangidae	present	present
Fam. Sclerosomatidae	present	present
Suborder Dyspnoi	present	present
Fam. Ischyropsalididae	absent	present
Fam. Sabaconidae	?absent (Nepal, Sechuan)	present
Fam. Taracidae	absent	present

Group	Region	
	Indomalayan	Palearctic
Fam. Dicranolasmatidae	absent	present
Fam. Trogulidae	absent	present
Fam. Nemastomatidae	Present (Thailand)	present
Fam. Nipponopsalididae	absent	present
Suborder Laniatores	present	present
Fam. Cladonychiidae	absent	Present (<i>Holoscotolemon</i>)
Fam. Travuniidae	absent	present
Fam. Triaenonychidae	absent	present
Fam. Assamiidae	present	absent
Fam. Biantidae	present	(Nepal, India)
Fam. Epedanidae	present	present
Fam. Petrobunidae	present	absent
Fam. Sandokanidae	present	absent
Fam. Tithaeidae	present	absent
Fam. Phalangodidae	absent	present
Fam. Podoctidae	present	Present (Japan, India)
Fam. Samoidae	present	absent
Fam. Zalmoxidae	present	absent
Fam. Paranonychidae	absent	present
Order Pseudoscorpiones	present	present
Suborder Epiocheirata	present	present
Fam. Chthoniidae	present	present
Fam. Tridenchthoniidae	present	present
Fam. Pseudotyranochthoniidae	absent China	present
Fam. Lechytiidae	present	present
Fam. Feallidae	Present (India)	absent
Suborder Iocheirata	present	present
Fam. Ideoroncidae	present	present
Fam. Hyidae	present	absent
Fam. Bochicidae	absent	present
Fam. Neobisiidae	present	present
Fam. Syarinidae	present	present
Fam. Parahyidae	present	absent
Fam. Garypidae	present	present
Fam. Geogarypidae	present	present
Fam. Larcidae	absent	present
Fam. Cheiridiidae	present	present
Fam. Pseudocheiridiidae	Present (India, Nepal)	absent
Fam. Olpiidae	present	present
Fam. Garypinidae	present	present
Fam. Menthiidae	absent	present
Fam. Sternophoridae	Present (India)	absent
Fam. Withiidae	present	present
Fam. Cheliferidae	present	present
Fam. Atemnidae	present	present

Table 1. Continued

Group	Region	Region	Group	Region	Region
	Indomalayan	Palearctic		Indomalayan	Palearctic
Fam. Chernetidae	present	present	Fam. Symphytognathidae	present	present
Order Araneae	present	present	Fam. Synsphyridae	absent	present
Suborder Mesothelae	present	present	Fam. Tetragnathidae	present	present
Fam. Liphistiidae	present	present	Fam. Nephilidae	present	present
Suborder Orthothelae	present	present	Fam. Theridiidae	present	present
Infraorder Mygalomorphae	present	present	Fam. Theridiosomatidae	present	present
Fam. Microstigmatidae	present	absent	Fam. Ctenidae	present	present
Fam. Hexathelidae (Macrothelinae)	present	present	Fam. Lycosidae	present	present
Fam. Dipluridae (Euagrinae)	present	present	Fam. Oxyopidae	present	present
Fam. Nemesiidae	present	present	Fam. Pisauridae	present	present
Fam. Theraphosidae	present	present	Fam. Psecridae	absent	present
Fam. Atypidae	present	present	Fam. Trechaleidae	absent	present
Fam. Antrodiaetidae	absent	present	Fam. Zoridae	present	present
Fam. Cyrtauchenidae	present	present	Fam. Zorocratidae	present	absent
Fam. Idiopidae	present	present	Fam. Zoropsidae	present	present
Fam. Ctenizidae	present	present	Fam. Agelenidae	present	present
Fam. Migidae	present	absent	Fam. Amaurobiidae	present	present
Infraorder Araneomorphae	present	present	Fam. Anyphaenidae	present	present
Fam. Hypochilidae	absent	present	Fam. Cybaeidae	absent	present
Fam. Austrochilidae	present	absent	Fam. Desidae	present	present
Fam. Filistatidae	present	present	Fam. Dictynidae	present	present
Fam. Drymusidae	present	absent	Fam. Hahniidae	present	present
Fam. Scytodidae	present	present	Fam. Sparassidae	present	present
Fam. Sicariidae	present	present	Fam. Selenopidae	present	present
Fam. Leptonetidae	absent	present	Fam. Zodariidae	present	present
Fam. Ochyroceratidae	present	?present (China)	Fam. Clubionidae	present	present
Fam. Telemidae	present	present	Fam. Miturgidae	present	present
Fam. Pholcidae	present	present	Fam. Phyxelididae	present	present
Fam. Caponiidae	present	absent	Fam. Titanocidae	absent	present
Fam. Tetrablemmidae	present	absent	Fam. Ammoxenidae	present	absent
Fam. Dysderidae	present	absent	Fam. Cithaeronidae	present	present
Fam. Oonopidae	present	present	Fam. Gallieniellidae	present	absent
Fam. Orsolobidae	present	absent	Fam. Gnaphosidae	present	present
Fam. Segestriidae	present	present	Fam. Prodidomidae	present	present
Fam. Eresidae	present	present	Fam. Trochanteriidae	present	present
Fam. Hersiliidae	present	present	Fam. Philodromidae	present	present
Fam. Oecobiidae	present	present	Fam. Thomisidae	present	present
Fam. Palpimanidae	present	present	Fam. Salticidae	present	present
Fam. Mimetidae	present	present	Fam. Corinnidae	present	present
Fam. Deinopidae	present	present	Fam. Liocranidae	present	present
Fam. Uloboridae	present	present	Order Opilioacarida	present	present
Fam. Anapidae	present	present	Fam. Opilioacaridae	present	present
Fam. Araneidae	present	present	Order Holothyrida	present	absent
Fam. Cyatholipidae	present	present	Fam. Holothyridae	present	absent
Fam. Linyphiidae	present	present	Order Ixodida	present	present
Fam. Sinopimoidae	absent	China (doubtful status)	Fam. Argasidae	present	present
			Fam. Ixodidae	present	present
			Order Mesostigmata	Present	present
			Order Sarcoptiformes	Present	present
			Order Trombidiformes	Present	present

Table 2. Comparison between the orders, suborders and families of Arachnida in the Indomalayan and Palearctic Regions

Order, Suborder	Indian	Malayan	Wallacea
Order Palpigradi	+	+	+
Order Ricinulei	-	-	-
Order Solifugae	+	+	-
Order Scorpiones	+	+	+
Order Amblypygi	+	+	+
Paleoamblypygi	-	-	-
Neoamblypygi	+	+	+
Order Uropygi	+	+	+
Order Schizomida	+	+	+
Order Pseudoscorpiones	+	+	+
Epiocheirata	+	+	+
Iocheirata	+	+	+
Order Opiliones	+	+	+
Cyphophthalmi	+	+	+
Eupnoi	+	+	+
Laniatores	+	+	+
Order Araneae	+	+	+
Mesothelae	-	+	-
Opisthothelae	+	+	+
Order Opilioacarida	+	+	-
Order Holothyrida	+	-	+
Order Mesostigmata	+	+	+
Order Ixodida	+	+	+
Order Trombidiformes	+	+	+
Order Sarcoptiformes	+	+	+

From West to East in the Palearctic the number of Solifugae is at first increasing: 60 sp. in the tiny Israel (LEVY & SHULOV, 1964 and suppl.), many others in Middle Asia and in Pakistan (POCOCK, 1895, LAWRENCE, 1956, HARVEY, 2013b). Some species of Galeodidae and Karschiidae are still present in Mongolia (*Galeodes kozlovi* Birula, *G. mongolicus* Roewer, *Karschia mongolica* Roewer) and East China (*Galeodes caspius caspius* Birula, *G. kozlovi* Birula, *G. montivagans* Roewer, *G. przewalskii* Birula, *G. rapax* Roewer, *G. sedulous* Roewer, *G. sejugatus* Roewer, *Karschia tibetana* Hirst), none is known from Siberia (BIRULA, 1938, GROMOV, 1998, 2000, 2004, HIRST, 1907, ROEWER, 1934). The distribution and the northern limit of Solifugae in Eurasia is shown on Map 2.

In the Indian Subregion 21 species of Solifugae are known. They belong to the families Galeodidae: Daesiidae – *Gluiopsis*, Galeodidae – *Galeodes*, Rhagodidae – *Rhagodima*, *Rhagoderma*, *Rhagodopa*, *Rhagodomma* (HARVEY, 2013b). The only member of Solifugae in SE Asia (Vietnam, Maluku – Melanoblossiidae) is *Dinorhax rostrumpsittaci*

(Simon, 1877) This species is the only one crossing the Wallace's Line to the East.

Scorpiones.

According to the catalogue of FET (1988) and other sources from the present territory of Russia (including Crimea) 5 species of scorpions are known. Very few scorpions are recorded from the Eastern Palearctic: three in Mongolia (*Mesobuthus caucasicus*, *M. eupeus*, *M. martensii*), some in northern China (DI & ZHU, 2013, FET, 2003, GROMOV, 1998, LOURENÇO, 2003, 2012, 2014, SHI & ZHANG, 2005, VACHON, 1953a, ZHU MS, QI JX, SONG DX, 2004, WU, 1936, QI, ZHU & LOURENÇO, 2005); in Japan – the widespread *Liocheles australasiae* (Hormuridae) and *Isometrus maculatus* (Buthidae), two from Korea (*Mesobuthus martensii* and *L. australasiae*) (TAKASHIMA (1941, 1945).

GROMOV (2001) outlined the northern limit of the distribution of scorpiones in Central Asia:

In South and South-East Asia 34 genera and seven families of scorpions are recorded: Bothriuridae (one genus), Buthidae (16 genera), Chaerilidae (one),

Map 2. Distribution of Solifugae in the world

Euscorpiidae (six), Hormuridae (six), Scorpionidae (two), Pseudochactidae (two genera) (FAGE, 1933, 1946; NENILIN & FET, 1992; PRENDINI, VOLSCHENK, MAALIKI & GROMOV, 2006; LOURENÇO, 2012). The most interesting recent discoveries were made from caves and concern the relict family Pseudochactidae. LOURENÇO (2007) added to the only known species of *Pseudochactas* Gromov from Central Asia another endemic genus and species, *Troglokhammouanus steineri* Lourenço, 2007 from a cave in Laos. A third genus and species, *Vietbocap canhi* Lourenço et Dinh-Sac Pham, 2010 was found in a cave in Vietnam, and one more species, also from cave (*Vietbocap thien-duongensis* Lourenço et Dinh-Sac Pham, 2010). They are all relicts. Two other cave scorpions of the genus *Euscorpiops* Vachon have been described from caves in Vietnam by LOURENÇO & DINH-SAC PHAM, 2013. Other scorpions described from caves are *Chaerilus pathom* Lourenço et Dinh-Sac Pham, 2014, and a new species of *Alloscorpiops* Vachon (LOURENÇO & DINH-SAC PHAM (2015).

In Table 2 is shown the distribution of the scorpion genera in the countries of South and South-East Asia.

Comprehensive analysis of the distribution of scorpions in South-East Asia and Wallacea was done by LOURENÇO (2014).

According to DI et al. (2011), the Yunnan Province has the biggest scorpion biodiversity in the whole of China (9 sp.).

From the Hainan Island have been recorded three widespread (DI et al., 2011) and two endemic species (*Mesobuthus martensii hainanensis* Birula and *Isometrus hainanensis* Lourenço, Qi et Zhu).

The numerous scorpions of India have been reviewed by TIKADER & BASTAWADE (1983), of Sri Lanka – by VACHON (1982)

Schizomida

The order is not recorded from the Palearctic.

In China (south) three recent species are known (Taiwan included), in Indonesia – three, in Malaysia – five, in Myanmar – three, in Singapore – three, in Sri Lanka – eight, in India – six, in Taiwan – two, in Thailand – one, in Ryukyu Islands – four. Altogether in South-East and South Asia there are 34 species of Schizomida of 12 genera (BASTAWADE, 1985, 2002, 2004; KULKARNI, 2012, COKENDOLPHER & TSURUSAKI, 1994; HARVEY, 1992, 2011, 2013b; KRAEPELIN, 1899; COKENDOLPHER, 1985, 1988, 1991, 1995; COKENDOLPHER & REDDELL, 1986, 1995, 2000; COKENDOLPHER, SISSOM & BASTAWADE, 1988; COKENDOLPHER & SITES, 1988; GRAVELY, 1910, 1911a, 1924; REDDELL & COKENDOLPHER, 1991; REMY, 1946; SISSOM, 1980). Comprehensive revisions of the order are done by ROWLAND (1972) and REDDELL & COKENDOLPHER (1995).

(Genera endemic for the Indomalayan Region in bold)

Fam. Hubbardiidae

Apozomus Harvey, 1992 – Australia, Borneo, New Guinea, Ryukyu Islands, Taiwan (17 sp., 7 in S. Asia)

Bamazomus Harvey, 1992 – Seychelles, Madagascar, Thailand, Hong Kong, Japan (Ryukyu Islands), West Malaysia, Papua New Guinea, Australia, Hawaii (two species in S. Asia)

Burmezomus Bastawade, 2004 – Burma (1 sp.)

Table 3. Scorpions in the Indomalayan Region

Country	India	Nepal	Bhut.	Banglad.	Burma	Sri Lanka	Mal.	Indon.
Number of species	117	11	4	5	11	15	27	29
Taxa								
Fam. Bothriuridae	+	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Cercophonius</i> Peters	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fam. Buthidae	+	+	-	+	+	+	+	+
<i>Androctonus</i> Ehrenb.	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Buthacus</i> Birula	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Buthoscorpio</i> Werner	4	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
<i>Charmus</i> Karsch	3	-	-	-	-	2	-	-
<i>Compsobuthus</i> Vachon	3	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hemibuthus</i> Pocock	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Himalayotitiobuthus</i> Lourenço	2	1	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Hottentotta</i> Birula	6	-	-	-	-	1	-	-
<i>Isometrus</i> Ehr.	13	1	-	1	-	6	3	7
<i>Lychas</i> C.L. Koch	15	4	-	-	4	1	5	6
<i>Mesobuthus</i> Vachon	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
<i>Odontobuthus</i> Vachon	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Orthochirus</i> Karsch	6	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Thaicharmus</i> Kovařík	2	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Vachonus</i> Tikader et Bastawade	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
Fam. Chaerilidae	+	+	-	+	-	+	+	+
<i>Chaerilus</i> Simon	6	2	-	1	-	1	11	8
Fam. Euscorpiidae	+	+	+	+	+	-	+	-
<i>Alloscorpiops</i> Vachon	-	-	-	-	1	-	-	-
<i>Dasyscorpiops</i> Vachon	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
<i>Euscorpiops</i> Vachon	4	-	2	1	4	-	-	-
<i>Neoscorpiops</i> Vachon	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Parascorpiops</i> Banks	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
<i>Scorpiops</i> Peters	10	2	2	1	-	-	-	-
Fam. Hormuridae	+	-	-	+	+	-	-	-
<i>Chiromachetes</i> Pocock	2	-	-	-	-	-	+	+
<i>Hormurus</i> Thorell	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	2
<i>Hormiops</i> Fage	-	-	-	-	-	-	1	-
<i>Iomachus</i> Pocock	4	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
<i>Liocheles</i> Sundevall	2	-	-	1	1	-	1	3
Fam. Scorpionidae	+	+	-	-	+	+	+	+
<i>Heterometrus</i> Ehr.	23	1	-	-	1	3	3	3
<i>Rugodentus</i> Bastawade et al.	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

Country	Thai.	Laos	Viet.	Camb.	Philip.	China	Hainan	
Number of sp.	20	15	25	5	14	[50]	5	
Taxa								
Fam. Buthidae	+	+	+	+	+	+	+	
<i>Hottentotta</i> Birula	-	-	-	-	-	2	-	
<i>Isometrus</i> Ehrenberg	3	1	3	1	2	3	2	

Table 3. Continued

<i>Lychas</i> C.L. Koch	3	4	1	1	3	2	1	
<i>Mesobuthus</i> Vachon	-	-	-	-	-	6	1	
<i>Orthochirus</i> Karsch	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	
<i>Thaicharmus</i> Kovařík	1	-	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Razianus</i> Farzanpay	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	
Fam. Chaerilidae	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	
<i>Chaerilus</i> Simon	2	1	6	1	3	8	-	
Fam. Euscorpiidae	+	+	+	-	-	+	-	
<i>Alloscorpiops</i> Vach.	2	2	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Euscorpiops</i> Vachon	3	2	5	-	-	11	-	
<i>Scorpiops</i> Peters	1	1	2	-	-	11	-	
Fam. Hormuridae	+	-	+	-	+	+	+	
<i>Hormiops</i> Fage	-	-	1	-	-	-	-	
<i>Hormurus</i> Thorell	-	-	-	-	2	-	-	
<i>Liocheles</i> Sundevall	1	-	1	-	1	1	1	
<i>Tibetiomachus</i> Lourenço et al.	-	-	-	-	-	1	-	
Fam. Scorpionidae	+	+	+	+	+	+	-	
<i>Heterometrus</i> Ehr.	4	2	4	2	3	3	-	
Fam. Pseudochactidae	-	+	+	-	-	-	-	
<i>Troglokhammouanus</i> Lourenço	-	1	-	-	-	-	-	
<i>Vietbocap</i> Lour. et Pham	-	1	2	-	-	-	-	

Clavizomus Reddell et Cokendolpher, 1995 – Java, West Malaysia, Singapore (one species)

Javazomus Reddell et Cokendolpher, 1995 – Java (one species)

Neozomus Reddell et Cokendolpher, 1995 – India (one species)

Oculozomus Reddell et Cokendolpher, 1995 – Sumatra (one species)

Orientzomus Cokendolpher et Tsurusaki, 1994 – Philippines (Luzon), Japan, Bonin Isl. (three species)

Ovozomus Harvey, 2001 – Seychelles, Ceylon, India, Mayotte, Cook Islands, Reunion (two species)

Schizomus Cook, 1899 – Sri Lanka etc. (12 species in S. Asia)

Trithyreus Kraepelin, 1899 – Burma (= Myanmar)(two species)

Zomus Reddell et Cokendolpher, 1995 – Malaysia (incl. Sarawak), Singapore, Seychelles, Rodrigues, Fiji, Samoa, Cook Islands; England (Kew Garden)(one species)

Uropygi (Thelyphonida)

The first comprehensive papers on the group were the revisions of POCOCK (1894) and KRAEPELIN (1897). Important contributions were made also by THORELL (1889), GRAVELY (1916), MELLO-LEITÃO (1931), WERNER (1935), SPEIJER (1933, 1936), ROWLAND (1973a, 1973b), HAUPT (1996, 2009), TARNANI (1901,

the northernmost Uropygi in the Far East of Russia, Palearctic), and others. Other northern representatives of the order (*Typopeltis*) live in Taiwan and the Ryukyu Islands (SCHWANGART, 1906, YOSHIKURA, 1973, HAUPT & DAXIANG SONG, 1996a). On the Philippines two endemic genera live (*Glyptogluteus* and *Thelyphonoides*), both on Panay Island.

ROWLAND & COOKE (1973) list 85 species in this order. HAUPT (2009) synonymised *Abaliella* Strand, *Minbosius* Speijer and *Tetrabalius* Thorell with *Thelyphonus* Latreille. KREHENWINKEL et al. (2009) described the new genus *Thelyphonoides* from Panay (Philippines). HAUPT & DAXIANG SONG (1996a, 1996b) revised the Uropygids of China, Japan and Thailand. According the calculations of HARVEY (2002b, 2003, 2013d) and the additions since this time, there are 110 species in the order Uropygi, belonging to 17 genera and two families (BLICK & HARVEY, 2011).

In South Asia ca. 78 species are recorded of eight genera of one family – the bulk of this family .

Fam. Thelyphonidae

Subfam. Thelyphoninae

Ginosigma Speijer, 1936 – Sunda Islands, Thailand, Cambodia, Vietnam (1 [2] species)

Glyptogluteus Rowland, 1973 – Philippines (Panay)(one species)

Apozomus - ■
Bamazomus - ▲
Burmezomus - ▼
Clavizomus - ●
Javazomus - ■
Neozomus - ●
Zomus - ☼
Oculozomus - ●
Orientzomus - ▼
Ovozomus - ◆
Schizomus - ◇
Trithyreus - □

Map 3. Distribution of Schizomida in Asia

Thelyphonoides Krehenwinkel et al., 2009 – Philippines (Panay)(one species)

Thelyphonus Latreille, 1802 (= *Abaliella* Strand, 1928 = *Minbosius* Speijer, 1936 = *Tetrabalius* Thorell, 1889 = *Chajnus* Speijer, 1936, fide HAUPT, 2009a) – Indonesia, Singapore, Cambodia, Philippines, Burma, Sri Lanka, India, Thailand, Borneo, Mollucas (30 species)

Subfam. Hypoctioninae

Hypoctonus Thorell, 1889 – Burma (Myanmar), South China, Malaysia, Thailand, Bangladesh, Java, India (19 species)

Labochirus Pocock, 1894 – India, Sri Lanka (four species)

Subfam. Uroproctinae

Uroproctus Pocock, 1894 – India – Assam, Cambodia, Bangladesh (one species)

Subfam. Typopeltinae – China, Russia, Taiwan, Japan, Thailand, Vietnam (11 species)

Typopeltis Pocock, 1894 (= *Teltus* Speijer, 1936)

– China, Russia, Taiwan, Hainan, Japan, Thailand, Vietnam (11 species)

Amblypygi

As a result of his visit to the Philippines in 1890, SIMON (1892) described the first Amblypygids from the islands, including the new genus *Sarax* (Charinidae). As a whole, on the Archipelago are represented three species of two genera and two families.

Fam. Charinidae

Sarax Simon, 1892 – *S. brachydactylus* Simon, 1892; *S. curioi* Giupponi et Miranda, 2012 (**end.**)

Fam. Charontidae

Charon Karsch, 1879 – *Ch. grayi* (Gervais, 1842)

These big and conspicuous, largely **cavernicolous**, dwellers of the warmer places have been subject to many articles (and, therefore, have many synonyms) by earlier researchers, starting with Linnaeus, Lamarck, Herbst, and also the researchers of 19th and early 20th centuries (Gervais, C.L. Koch, L. Koch, Bilimek, Karsch, Pocock, Butler, Kraepelin,

■ - *Typopeltis* Pocock
 △ - *Labochirus* Pocock
 ▼ - *Uroproctus* Pocock
 ▲ - *Hypoctonus* Thorell
 ◇ - *Thelyphonus* Latreille

○ - *Thelyphonoides* Krehenwinkel et al.
 ◉ - [*Minbosius* Speijer] = *Thelyphonus*
 ◆ - *Ginosigma* Speijer
 ● - *Glyptogluteus* Rowland

Map 4. Distribution of Uropygi in Asia

Simon, Gravely, Thorell, Hansen and others). Many contributions on the Amblypygi of the Indomalayan Region have been made in the last 120 years by Fage, Rowland, Harvey, Rahmadi, and other authors (THORELL, 1889, KRAEPELIN, 1895, GRAVELY, 1911b, 1911c, FAGE, 1946, RAHMADI & HARVEY, 2008, RAHMADI, HARVEY & KOJIMA, 2010, 2011, ROEWER, 1928).

The papers of QUINTERO (1983, 1986) and, especially the revisions of WEYGOLDT (2000 and others) are the basis of the modern understanding of the order, containing now (HARVEY, 2003, 136 species, BLICK & HARVEY, 2011; updated in 2016 – 180 species) of 17 genera and five families. In the Palearctic Region (in Eurasia) is known two species from Greece (Rhodes, Kos), Turkey, Israel, and Egypt (*Charinus ioanniticus*, *Ch. israelensis*). In the Indomalayan Region are known at least 25 species of seven genera and four families:

Suborder Euamblypygi

Fam. Charinidae

Catageus Thorell, 1889 – Burma (Myanmar) (one species)

Charinus Simon, 1892 (= *Charinides* Gravely,

= *Enantiosarax* Mello-Leitão, = *Oligacanthophrynus* Caporiacco, = *Lindosiella* Kritscher) – Greece (Rhodes, Kos), Turkey, Egypt, Israel, Andaman Islands, India, W. Samoa, Vanuatu, Indonesia (Java, Borneo), Singapore, Malaysia (one species). One species of *Charinus* has been described (WEYGOLDT, 2005) from Pakistan (the border between the Palearctic and Indomalayan Regions).

Sarax Simon, 1892 (= *Phrynichosarax* Gravely) – Malaysia, Singapore, Philippines (Luzon), Indonesia (Java, Kalimantan), India, Andaman Islands, Vietnam, Laos, Cambodia, Borneo (eight species)

Fam. Charontidae

Charon Karsch, 1879 – Indonesia (Java, Maluku, Sumbawa), Malaysia (incl. Borneo), Palau, Philippines, Singapore (one species)

Stygophrynus Kraepelin, 1895 – Burma, Thailand, Vietnam, Malaysia, Indonesia (Java, Sumatra, Kalimantan)(seven species)

Fam. Phrynichidae

Subfam. Phrynichinae

Phrynichus Karsch, 1879 (= *Myodalis* Simon) – Sri Lanka, India, Thailand, Cambodia, Malaysia, Vietnam (six species)

- | | |
|-----------------------|-------------------------|
| ■ - <i>Phrynichus</i> | ◇ - <i>Charon</i> |
| ● - <i>Damon</i> | ◆ - <i>Stygophrynus</i> |
| X - <i>Charinus</i> | ! - <i>Phrynus</i> |
| □ - <i>Sarax</i> | - <i>Catageus</i> |

Map 5. Distribution of Amblypygi in Asia and East Africa

Fam. Phrynidae

Phrynus Lamarck, 1801 (= *Admetus* C.L. Koch, = *Neophrynus* Kraepelin) – Indonesia (Flores) (one species)

Pseudoscorpiones.

In Eastern Palearctic pseudoscorpions of the families Chthoniidae, Neobisiidae, Syarinidae, Geogarypidae, Atemnidae, Olpiidae, Cheiridiidae, Chernetidae, Cheliferidae, Withiidae are recorded (HARVEY, 1990, 2011, 2013a, with suppl.; DASHDAMIROV, 2004; DASHDAMIROV & SCHAWALLER, 1985, 1986, 1989, 1993a, 1993b).

From Mongolia have been recorded 23 species of 14 genera and the families Neobisiidae, Atemnidae, Cheliferidae, Chernetidae, Withiidae. The most widespread is *Dactylochelifer* Beier (seven species) (BEIER, 1973b).

From Russia are recorded only 33 species (SCHAWALLER, 1985, 1986, 1989, 1994a; DASHDAMIROV & SCHAWALLER, 1992, 1993a, 1993b, REDIKORZEV, 1949)

From South Korea are known 18 species of 11 genera and the families Chthoniidae, Neobisiidae, Cheiridiidae and Chernetidae (LEE, 1981). No data about North Korea is found.

Some **endemic genera** in the Eastern Palearctic are:

Fam. Cheliferidae

Gobichelifer Krumpál, 1979

The pseudoscorpions of the Himalaya correspond to the transitional character of this huge mountain massif (ČURČIĆ, 1980; SCHAWALLER, 1983, 1987, 1988, 1991).

In Palearctic Japan (without Ryukyu and Bonin Islands) 58 species of 29 genera and 12 families are known, thanks to Ellingsen, Beier, Morikawa, Sato, Chamberlin, Sakayori. There are 43 endemic species (ca. 72%), but only one **endemic genus**: *Nipponogarypus* Morikawa (HARVEY, 1990, 1992, 2011, 2013a).

In South-East Asia are recorded pseudoscorpions belonging to 21 families: Chthoniidae, Lechtyiidae, Feaelidae, Tridenchthoniidae, Ideoroncidae, Sernophoridae, Atemnidae, Hyidae, Gymnobisiidae, Neobisiidae, Syarinidae, Parahyidae, Pseudochiridiidae, Geogarypidae, Garypinidae, Garypidae, Olpiidae, Cheiridiidae, Cheliferidae, Chernetidae, Withiidae. From them 16 families are represented in the Palearctic Region. Absent from the Palearctic Region are Feaelidae, Hyidae, Parahyidae, Pseudochiridiidae and Sternophoridae. Only **Parahyidae** of these families is **endemic** for the Indomalayan Region (BEIER, 1951, 1966, 1973a, REDIKORZEV, 1938; DASHDAMIROV, 2007; SCHAWALLER, 1994b, 1995).

Map 6. Distribution of fam. Stylocellidae

Number of Pseudoscorpion species known in some of the countries in the area:

Burma (Myanmar) – 13; Thailand – 43; Vietnam – 62; Laos – nine; Cambodia – 15; Malaysia – 35 (HARVEY, 2013a). It is clear that in most of these countries many more pseudoscorpions are expected to be recorded.

Endemic pseudoscorpion genera in South-East Asia are:

Fam. Garypinidae

Caecogarypinus Dashdamirov, 2007 – Vietnam (one species)

Fam. Parahyidae

Parahya Beier – Singapore, the Caroline Islands

Fam. Ideoroncidae

Shravana Chamberlin, 1930 – Thailand (one species)

Fam. Cheliferidae

Tetrachelifer Beier, 1967 – Vietnam (two species)

From the Andaman Islands BEIER (1981) recorded three species: *Xenolpium madagascariense* (Beier), known from Madagascar and Aldabra, *Anagarypus oceanusindicus* Chamberlin, known from Aldabra and Chagos Archipelago, and *Pseudochiridium clavigerum* (Thorell), known from India and Indonesia.

From the extrapaleartic islands of Japan are known 10 species, all **endemic**.

Opiliones

Cyphophthalmi

In the Eastern Palearctic the suborder Cyphophthalmi is known only from Japan (*Suzukielus sauteri* Roewer) – **endemic genus** *Suzukielus* Juberthie.

In South-East Asia five of the six genera of fam. Stylocellidae are represented, two of them **endemic** (THORELL, 1882, 1890, RAMBLA, 1991, 1994, GIRIBET, 2000, CLOUSE, 2012, CLOUSE et al., 2011, SCHWENDINGER & GIRIBET, 2005, SHARMA & GIRIBET, 2009, CLOUSE & GIRIBET, 2010, SHEAR, 1993, CLOUSE, DE BIVORT & GIRIBET, 2010):

Subfam. **Fangensinae** (end.)

Fangensis Rambla, 1994 – Thailand (three species)

Giribetia Clouse, 2012 – Thailand (one species)

Subfam. Stylocellinae

Leptopsalis Thorell, 1882 – Malaya (three species)

Stylocellus Westwood, 1874 – Malaya (one species)

Miopsalis Thorell, 1890 – Malaya (two species)

The species are also **endemic**, mostly known from the type localities.

Three genera of fam. Stylocellidae are recorded from the Malay Archipelago (19 species):

Leptopsalis Thorell, 1882 – Sumatra (three species), Java (two species), Sulawesi (four species)

Stylocellus Westwood, 1874 – Sumatra (one species)

Miopsalis Thorell, 1890 – Borneo (nine species)

Two species of *Stylocellus* Westwood have been found in the western part of New Guinea, crossing thus the Lydekker's line (CLOUSE & GIRIBET, 2007).

In Sri Lanka live three species of the endemic genus *Pettalus* Thorell, 1876 (fam. Pettalidae, known also from Madagascar, Chile, South Africa, Australia and New Zealand) (SHARMA & GIRIBET, 2006, SHARMA, KARUNARATHNA & GIRIBET, 2009). From India (Arunachal Pradesh) has been described an endemic genus and species *Meghalaya annandalei* Giribet, Sharma et Bastawade, 2007 (Stylocellidae). The family Pettalidae is not known so far from the Asiatic continent (GIRIBET, 2000 and suppl.).

Dyspnoi

The Eastern Palearctic is inhabited by members of the families Sabaconidae, Nemastomatidae, and Nipponopsalididae, are also by a few Ischyropsalididae and Trogulidae. Two more families (Dicranolasmatidae and Taracidae) are dwellers of the Western Palearctic and U.S.A. (SCHÖNHOFER, 2013).

Fam. Sabaconidae with the only genus *Sabacon* Simon is widespread (U.S.A., Europe, Japan, China, Siberia, Altai; several species have been described from Nepal – the high Himalaya up to above 5000 m, which form part of the boundary between the Palearctic and Indo-Malayan Regions). TSURUSAKI & DAXIANG SONG (1993b) published two new species of *Sabacon* from Sichuan Province (China).

Fam. Ischyropsalididae – found east of Tajikistan

Fam. Nemastomatidae – in the Eastern Palearctic the genera *Mediostoma* Kratochvil (Iran, Tajikistan) and *Starengovia* Snegovaya (Kirghizstan) reach the mountains of Central Asia

Fam. Nipponopsalididae – three species of genus *Nipponopsalis* Martens et Suzuki from Korea and Japan (including Ryukyus and the Kuril Islands) (SCHÖNHOFER, 2013).

Fam. Trogulidae – east of northern Iran (SCHÖNHOFER, 2013).

Only two species of Dyspnoi from a genus of the family Nemastomatidae are recorded from South-East Asia. *Cladolasma* [*Dendrolasma*] *angka* (Schwendinger et Gruber, 1992) (Ortholasmatinae) in Thailand is the second recorded species of the genus *Cladolasma* Suzuki; the other species is *C. parvulum* Suzuki from Japan. Another *Cladolasma* (*C. damingshan* Zhang et Zhang (ZHANG & ZHANG, 2013) was described from Guangxi, China (the first

representative of Nemastomatidae in China). The Dyspnoi are missing from the Indomalayan Region.

TSURUSAKI & DAXIANG SONG. 1993a. Occurrence of *Crosbycus dasygnemus* in China

SUZUKI (1972) analysed some other cases of discontinuous distribution of opilions.

Eupnoi

In the Eastern Palearctic members of the families Caddidae, Phalangiidae and Sclerosomatidae have been found (GRICENKO, 1979a, GRITSENKO, 1979b, 1980; STAREGA, 1978; TSURUSAKI et al., 2000).

Fam. Caddidae – only one species of genus *Caddo* Banks (otherwise North American) is known from Japan. Even the species *Caddo agilis* Banks is shared between Japan and North America (SUZUKI & TSURUSAKI, 1983).

Fam. Phalangiidae – genera, represented in the Eastern Palearctic: *Lacinius* Thorell (China), *Mitopus* Thorell (Japan, Mongolia), *Oligolophus* C.L.Koch (China), *Egaenus* C.L. Koch (Karakorum, Iran, Mongolia, Siberia, Tajikistan, Uzbekistan), *Homolophus* Banks (Altai, Korea, Siberia, Mongolia, China, Kazakhstan), *Opilio* Herbst (China, Mongolia, Iran, Japan, Kuril Island, Karakorum, Kazakhstan), *Scleropilio* Roewer (= *Scutopilio* Roewer) (Central Asia), *Acanthomegabunus* Tsurusaki et al. (Siberia), *Liropilio* Gritsenko (Kazakhstan, Russia), *Phalangium* L. (? China), *Rilaena* Šilhavý (Iran), *Thapinius* Roewer (Kamtchatka), *Pamirphalangium* Starega (Pamir, nomen nudum). Many of these genera are known also from Europe. *Himalphalangium* was described by J. Martens from Nepal (the Himalaya), where the Eastern Palearctic meets the Indomalayan Region. Other important papers on the Opilions of the Himalaya are done by MARTENS (1980 and others).

Fam. Sclerosomatidae – genera, represented in the Eastern Palearctic: *Gagrellula* Roewer (China, Japan), *Harmanda* Roewer (Nepal), *Harmandina* (China), *Psathyropus* L. Koch (Japan, Far East of Russia), *Pseudogagrella* Redikorzev (China), *Systemocentrus* Simon (Japan), *Leiobunum* C.L. Koch (Japan), *Nelima* Roewer (Japan), *Pseudohomalenotus* Caporiacco (Karakorum), *Pygobunus* Roewer (Japan). Many of these genera are known also from Europe.

Some genera (*Himaldroma*, *Nepalgrella*, *Nepalkanchia*, *Gyoidea*) were described by J. Martens from Nepal in the Himalaya (MARTENS, 1983, 1984 and others). Tsurusaki (1991) reported opilions from Taiwan.

From South-East Asia are recorded many species of Eupnoi of the families Phalangiidae and

Sclerosomatidae, particularly Gagrellinae (many papers of Thorell, Roewer, Suzuki and other authors).

Some **endemic genera** are:

Mitopiella Banks; *Adungrella* Roewer, *Akalpia* Roewer, *Altobunus* Roewer, *Antigrella* Roewer; *Aurivilliola* Roewer; *Bakerinulus* Roewer; *Bastia* Roewer; *Baturitia* Roewer; *Biceropsis* Roewer; *Bonthainia* Roewer; *Bullobunus* Roewer; *Carinobius* Roewer; *Carmichaelus* Roewer *Ceratobunellus* Roewer; *Ceratobunoides* Roewer; *Cervibunus* Roewer; *Chasenella* Roewer; *Chebabi* Roewer; *Coonoora* Roewer; *Dentobunus* Roewer, *Diangathia* Roewer, *Echinobunus* Roewer; *Euceratobunus* Roewer, 1923; *Eugagrella* Roewer; *Euzaleptus* Roewer; *Gagrella* Stoliczka; *Gagrellenna* Roewer; *Gagrellina* Roewer; *Gagrellissa* Roewer; *Gagrellopsis* Sato et Suzuki; *Gagrellula* Roewer; *Globulosoma* Martens; *Hamitergum* Crawford; *Harmanda* Roewer; *Harmandina* Schenkel; *Hehoa* Roewer; *Heterogagrella* Roewer; *Hexazaleptus* Suzuki; *Himaldroma* Martens; *Himalzaleptus* Martens; *Hologagrella* Roewer; *Hypogrella* Roewer; *Koyamaia* Suzuki; *Marthana* Thorell; *Melanopa* Thorell; *Melanopella* Roewer; *Melanopula* Roewer; *Metadentobunus* Roewer; *Metahehoa* Suzuki; *Metasyleus* Roewer; *Metaverpulus* Roewer; *Metazaleptus* Roewer; *Microzaleptus* Roewer, *Neogagrella* Roewer, *Nepalgrella* Martens, *Nepalkanchia* Martens, *Obigrella* Roewer, *Octozaleptus* Suzuki, *Oobunus* Kishida, *Orissula* Roewer, *Padangrella* Roewer, *Palniella* Roewer, *Paradentobunus* Roewer, *Paragagrella* Roewer, *Paragagrellina* Schenkel, *Paraumbogrella* Suzuki, *Pergagrella* Roewer, *Pokhara* Suzuki, *Prodentobunus* Roewer, *Psathyropus* L. Koch, *Pseudarthromerus* Karsch, *Pseudogagrella* Redikorzev, *Pseudomelanopa* Suzuki, *Pseudosystemocentrus* Suzuki, *Sarasinia* Roewer, *Sataria* Roewer, *Scotomenia* Thorell, *Sericicorpus* Martens, *Sinadroma* Roewer, *Syleus* Thorell, *Syngagrella* Roewer, *Systemocentrus* Simon, *Tetraceratobunus* Roewer, *Toragrella* Roewer, *Umbogrella* Roewer, *Umbopilio* Roewer, *Verpulus* Simon, *Verrucobunus* Roewer, *Xerogrella* Martens, *Zaleptiolus* Roewer, *Zaleptulus* Roewer, *Zaleptus* Thorell

Laniatores

From the South-East Asia and the Malayan Archipelago Laniatores from more than 50 genera are recorded, including the families Assamiidae, Biantidae, Podoctidae, Epedanidae, **Sandokanidae** (= Oncopodidae), Phalangodidae, Zalmoxidae, **Tithaeidae**, **Petrobunidae** (KURY, PÉREZ-CLOUSE, DE BIVORT & GIRIBET, 2009, MARTENS

& SCHWENDINGER, 1998, SHARMA et al., 2013, SCHWENDINGER, 1992, 2006, SCHWENDINGER & MARTENS, 2006, WANG, 1941). The families in **bold** are endemic for the Indomalayan Region. Most of the others are not found in the Palearctic Region. Other families (Phalangodidae) are considered by some researchers to be relicts in the Palearctic. Other specialists (MARTENS, 1972) disagree with the relict character of the European Phalangodidae.

Among the authors having worked on the South-East Asian Laniatores we should note TSURUSAKI (1995), SCHWENDINGER (1992, 2006), SHARMA et al. (2012), SHARMA & GIRIBET (2011), SUZUKI (1969, 1977a, 1977b, 1982, 1985), ROEWER (1912, 1927, 1931, 1935, 1938, 1940, 1949), Thorell and other authors.

Endemic genera are:

Fam. Assamiidae

Assamiinae

Assamiella Roewer, 1912 – Burma (one species)

Neassamia Roewer, 1935 – Thailand (one species)

Pechota Roewer, 1935 – Malacca (one species)

Popassamia Roewer, 1940 – Burma (one species)

Tavoybia Roewer, 1935 – Malacca (one species)

Dampetrinae

Cadomea Roewer, 1940 – Malaysia (one species)

Dongmolla Roewer, 1927 – Vietnam (one species)

Mermerus Thorell, 1876 – Java, Borneo (two species)

Nothippulus Roewer, 1923 – Vietnam (one species)

Nothippus Thorell, 1890 – Sumatra, Malakka (three species)

Pahangius Roewer, 1935 – Malakka (one species)

Paradampetrus Giltay, 1930 – Sumatra (one species)

Sudaria Roewer, 1923 – Sumatra, Simalur, Sulawesi (four species)

Fam. Podoctidae

Dongmoa Roewer, 1927 – Vietnam

Heteroibalonus Goodnight et Goodnight, 1947 (one species)

Mesoceratula Roewer, 1949 (one species)

Podoctellus Roewer, 1949 – Malaysia (Johore) (one species)

Podoctis Thorell, 1890 – Pinang (one species)

Sibolgia Roewer, 1923 – Malaya (one species)

Stobitus Roewer, 1949 – Malaya (one species)

Fam. Petrobunidae

Petrobunus Sharma et Giribet, 2011 – Philippines (three species)

Fam. Tithaeidae – 38 species

Istithaeus Roewer, 1949 – Borneo

Kondosus Roewer, 1949 – Borneo
Metatithaeus Suzuki, 1969 – Borneo
Sterrhosoma Thorell, 1891 – Sumatra
Tithaeomma Roewer, 1949 – Burma
Tithaeus Thorell, 1890 – Burma, Thailand, Malaya, Singapore, Sumatra, Krakatau, Java, Borneo, Sarawak, Timor

Fam. Epedanidae
Epedaninae
Alloepedanus Suzuki, 1985 – Thailand (one species)
Caletorellus Roewer, 1938 – Thailand (one species)
Epedanidus Roewer, 1945 – Malaysia (Perak) (one species)
Euepedanus Roewer, 1915 – Thailand, Malacca (seven species)
Heteroepedanus Roewer, 1912 – (two species)
Paratakaioia Suzuki, 1985 – Thailand (two species)
Plistobunus Pocock, 1903 – Hong Kong, Hainan Island (two species)
Pseudoepeidanus Suzuki, 1969 – (one species)
Pseudomarthana P. D. Hillyard, 1985 – Malaysia (one species)
Thyreotus Thorell, 1889 – Burma (two species)
Toccolus Roewer, 1927 – Vietnam (“Tonking”), etc. (three species)
Zepedanulus Roewer, 1927 – Malacca, Thailand, etc. (four species)

Acrobuninae
Heterobiantes Roewer, 1912 – Hong Kong (one species)
Paracrobanus Suzuki, 1977 – (two species)

Sarasinicinae
Gintingius Roewer, 1938 – Pahang (Malaya) (one species)
Panticola Roewer, 1938 – (placement is uncertain) Malacca (one species)
Pasohnus Suzuki, 1976 – was in Phalangodidae (one species)
Sembilanus Roewer, 1938 – Malacca (one species)
Siponnus Roewer, 1927 – Pulu Pinang (one species)
Sungstotia Tsurusaki, 1995 – Vietnam (one species)
Tonkinatus Roewer, 1938 – Vietnam (Tonking) (one species)

Incertae sedis
Buparellus Roewer, 1949 – Burma, Thailand (4 species)
Gasterapophus Zhang, Lian et Zhang, 2015 – Hainan (two species)

Fam. Zalmoxidae

Zalmoxis Soerensen in not endemic, but this is the only genus of Zalmoxidae in the Old World, with ca. 15 species in South Asia, incl. the Philippines (SHARMA et al., 2012).

Fam. Sandokanidae (Oncopodidae) – 71 species

Sandokan Thorell, 1876 – SE Asia (10 species)

Gnomulus Thorell, 1890 – SE Asia, India, S.China (53 species)

Caenoncopus Martens et Schwendinger, 1998 – Sumatra (three species)

Palaeoncopus Martens et Schwendinger, 1998 – Sumatra (three species)

Biantoncopus Martens et Schwendinger, 1998 – Leyte, Philippines (one species)

Martensiellus Schwendinger, 2006 – Borneo (one species)

“The distribution of Sandokanidae appears to be limited principally by this group’s dispersal ability. Four other laniatorid families, Assamiidae, Epedanidae, Podoctidae, and Zalmoxidae, are distributed throughout Sundaland, but all of these have greater range than Sandokanidae, and frequently demonstrate clear dispersal events (GIRIBET AND KURY, 2007). The restriction of Sandokanidae to Sundaland and the Philippines is suggestive of diversification in accordance with the breakup of Sundaland’s components” (SHARMA & GIRIBET, 2009).

The opilionids of the Kuril Islands have been analysed by TSURUSAKI & CRAWFORD (2001), the ones from the Ryukyus – by SUZUKI (1971, 1973).

Araneae

From the spiders there are 69 families inhabiting the Palearctic Region and 71 fam. in the Indo-Malayan Region, with 60 families that are common for both regions (World Spider Catalog 2015). Interesting is the case of the relict family Liphystiidae, the only member of the suborder Mesothelae. This family is found in Japan, China and South-East Asia. According to XU X et al. (2015), these spiders are “living fossils” and the suborder Mesothelae is an ancient clade, sister of all modern spiders. Again according these authors, Liphystiidae genera have originated in Asia in the Paleogene (4-24 Ma).

This timing is relatively recent, taking into account the old age of the spider divergence (297.6 Ma) between the Mesothelae and the Opisthothelae (Mygalomorphae and Araneomorphae). The existence of Mesothelae in Japan (Kyushu and Ryukyu Islands) is explained by HAUPT (2003) “through vicariant origin in the Tertiary when the Japanese island arc separated from mainland Asia, or alterna-

tively, as a consequence of dispersal events over land bridges from East China during the Pleistocene”.

Other 10 families, represented in the Eastern Palearctic, but not in the Western, are Dipluridae, Antrodiaetidae (U.S.A. and Japan), Hypochilidae (U.S.A. and China), Symphytognathidae, Nephilidae, Ctenidae, Psechridae, Trechaleidae (America and Japan), Desidae, Trochanteriidae. Most of them are connected with the fauna of the Indo-Malayan Region. Some families indicate a disjunction (usually wide gap) between the Eastern and the Western Palearctic Regions. Such disjunction is known for many other groups of animals. It is due to the aridisation, orogenesis and the deforestation in the central parts of Eurasia (ANDREEVA, 1975, KRIZHANOVSKIJ, 1965).

Important reviews of spiders of Central Asia and Siberia are collated also by MIKHAILOV & FET (1994), ESKOV (1986a, 1986b), MARUSIK & KOPONEN (2002), IZMAILOVA (1989) and many others.

The spiders of the high mountains (Himalaya, Karakorum), which are on the border or the transition zone between the Palearctic and the Indomalayan Regions, have been studied by many specialists, i.e. CAPORIACCO, 1935, JÄGER, 2001, ZHANG, ZHU & SONG, 2006. The spiders, pseudoscorpions and scorpions of some other high mountains in the southern part of the Eastern Palearctic (Tibet, Altai, Tien Shan) are subject of the studies of MAHNERT, 1977, LOURENÇO, 2003, LOURENÇO et al., 2005, TANASEVITCH, 1989, QI JIAN-XIN, MING-SHENG ZHU & LOURENÇO, 2005, and many others.

Many papers (SIMON, 1901, KAYASHIMA, 1955, DEELEMAN – REINHOLD, 1995, 2000, JÄGER, 2001, 2005, JÄGER & YIN, 2001, JÄGER & PRAXAYSOMBATH, 2009, SAITO & ONO, 2001, SONG, ZHU & CHEN, 1999, TANIKAWA, 2009, TANIKAWA & ONO, 2009, WANG XIN-PING, GRISWOLD & MILLER, 2010, WANG CREWS & HARVEY, 2011, XIN-PING & MARTENS, 2009, and others) deal with the spiders of South and South-East Asia. The arachnofauna of India, Ceylon and Burma has been analysed by POCOCK (1900), followed by many other authors (i.e. BEIER, 1973a, SHARMA et al., 2009, COKENDOLPHER et al., 1988, GRAVELY, 1910, 1911a, 1911c, SILIWAL, MOLUR & BISWAS, 2005, TIKADER, 1970, 1977, 1987). The spiders of Japan were studied by TANIKAWA (2009), TANIKAWA & ONO (2009), SHIMOJANA (1977, 1981), BRIGNOLI (1970), NISHIKAWA (2009), OKUMURA et al. (2009), SAITO & ONO (2001), ONO H. (Ed.) (2009). The spiders of Korea have been discussed mainly by PAIK (1967) and NAMKUNG et al. (2009). The information on the Chinese spiders was presented by SONG D. X., ZHU, M. S. & J. CHEN (1999), but in the last

decades many Chinese scientists (i.e. WANG XIN-PING, GRISWOLD & MILLER, 2010, ZHU & ZHANG, 2008) published descriptions of many new taxa and important theoretical papers as the ones by MENG, LI & MURPHY, 2008 and HUANG ZHENGUO & ZHANG WEIQIANG, 2003.

According to the checklist of STENCHLY (2011), from Indonesia and New Guinea have been registered 58 families of spiders with 505 genera and 1954 species; 499 species being found only in New Guinea. Six of the 58 families (Dipluridae, Lamponidae, Micropholcommatidae, Nicodamidae, Stiphidiidae, Titanoecidae) are found only in New Guinea.

Opilioacarida.

The small order Opilioacarida (37 species) is represented in the Eastern Palearctic only by the species *Paracarus hexophthalmus* (Redikorzev), described from Middle Asia (REDIKORZEV, 1937). Another species of *Paracarus* has been described from Baltic amber (*P. pristinus* Dunlop, Wunderlich et Poinar, 2004). In the Indomalayan Region there is one endemic genus (*Indiacarus* Das et Bastawade) found in India (DAS & BASTAWADE, 2007).

Trombidiformes

Fam. Eutrombiidae

From Vietnam MAKOL & GABRYŚ (2005) described the new endemic subfamily *Caecothrombiinae*.

Holothyrida.

The Holothyrids are found in New Guinea, Lord Howe I. and New Caledonia (BERON, 2014, LEHTINEN, 1980, 1991, 1995). In the Indomalayan Region they are known only from Sri Lanka (end. genus and species *Indothyrys greeni* Lehtinen, 1995). The absence on these big and conspicuous mites from the continent and the islands between Sri Lanka and New Guinea is remarkable. They are absent also from the Palearctic Region, Africa and Madagascar.

Ixodida

Fam. Argasidae

The two widespread genera (*Argas*, *Ornithodoros*) are common for the Palearctic and the Indomalayan Regions, no endemic genera.

Fam. Ixodidae

Besides the widespread genera like *Amblyomma*, *Dermacentor*, *Haemaphysalis*, *Ixodes*, *Rhipicephalus*, in the mountains of the South Palearctic live two or three species of the genus *Anomalohimalaya* Hoogstraal, Kaiser et Mitchell (Nepal, Pamir, Tadjikistan, China) (GUGLIELMONE et al., 2010).

The other orders and suborders of Acari are less known in the described area and will not be treated in this article.

Conclusion.

Most families (at least 90) of Arachnida (from Acari is included only Opilioacaridae) are common for both regions. There are **no endemic orders or suborders** in any of them. Regarding the Arachnida, their distribution does not justify the sharp difference between the two kingdoms (Paleotropical and Holarctic) in Eastern Eurasia. The transitional zone

(Sino-Japanese Realm) of HOLT et al. (2013) also does not satisfy the criteria for outlining an area on the same footing as the Palearctic and Indomalayan Realms.

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Арахногеографски анализ на границата между Палеарктичната и Индомалайската области

Петър БЕРОН

(Резюме)

Статията проследява как (и дали) разпространението на разните разреди от Arachnida следва класическото поделение на Азия и къде минава линията (преходната зона) между Източна Палеарктика (Холарктичното царство) и Индомалайската област (Палеотропика). Тази граница включва пустинята Тар, Каракорум, Хималаите, ивица в Централен Китай и линията северно от Тайван и островите Рюкю.

Анализът на всички разреди на Arachnida показва, че повечето семейства (90, от акарите в анализа са включени само Oribiioacaridae, Holothyridae, Ixodidae and Argasidae) са общи за Палеарктичната и Индомалайската области. В никоя от двете територии няма ендемични разреди или подразреди. Така че, що се отнася до Arachnida, тяхното разпространение не показва такава голяма разлика, каквато би могла да се очаква между две царства (Палеотропика и Холарктика) в Източна Евразия. Преходната зона (Sino-Japanese Realm) на Holt et al. (2013) също не задоволява критериите за очертаване на област със същия ранг като Палеарктичния и Индомалайския „Realms“.